

Highlights

Surface water and shallow groundwater samples were collected from the Lut Desert, one of the hottest places on Earth

Water composition shows evidence for extensive evapoconcentration and precipitation/dissolution of salts.

Weathering of silicates also contributes solutes to these brines.

Waters have high NO_3^- suggesting accumulation of NO_3^- from the atmosphere

1 The Hydrogeochemistry of Shallow Groundwater from Lut Desert, Iran: The
2 Hottest Place on Earth

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22

23 **ABSTRACT**

24 This paper presents the first shallow groundwater geochemical data from the Lut Desert (Dasht-e-Lut),
25 one of the hottest places on the planet. The waters are Na-Cl brines that have undergone extensive
26 evaporation, but they are unlike seawater derived brines in that the K^+ is low and the $Ca^{2+} > Mg^{2+}$ and
27 $HCO_3^- > SO_4^{2-}$. In addition to evapo-concentration, the most saline samples indicate that the dissolution
28 of previously deposited salt also acts as a major control on the geochemistry of these waters. High
29 concentrations of gypsum in surface soils along with the water geochemistry indicate the dissolution,
30 precipitation, and reprecipitation of evaporite salts are very important to the overall chemistry of the near
31 surface environment. As demonstrated by the high H_4SiO_4 concentrations, the weathering of
32 aluminosilicate minerals also contributes to the solutes present. Fixed nitrogen ($NO_3^-+NO_2^-$)
33 concentrations suggest little to no denitrification is occurring in these waters. The processes controlling
34 the geochemistry of the Lut waters are similar to those in other hyperarid regions of the Earth.

35 **INTRODUCTION**

36 The Lut Desert (Dasht-e-Lut) in southeast Iran is one of the largest deserts in Iran, receiving < 30 mm of
37 precipitation annually. Its bioclimate is classified as 'tropical hyperdesertic,' the hottest and driest
38 bioclimate in the world in the Global Bioclimatic Classification (Djamali et al., 2011). The region has
39 been referred to as the thermal pole of the Earth and is recognized as one of the hottest, if not the hottest,
40 locations on planet Earth with surface temperatures as high as 70.7 °C recorded via satellite in the mid
41 2000's (Mildrexler et al., 2006). A recent measurement during the sampling campaign in Yalan dunes
42 (March 4, 2017) returned skin temperature as high as 78.2 °C (Trescher, 2017). The mean annual
43 precipitation (7-year average, 2003-2010) recorded at the nearest meteorological station, Shahdad
44 synoptic weather station, located at the west flank of the Lut desert with the altitude of 400 m.a.s.l, does
45 not exceed 30 mm. Precipitation is highest from January through March and the dry season lasts from
46 April to November. Mean annual temperature at the station is 27.5°C and the mean minimum and
47 maximum daily air temperatures of the warmest and coldest months of the year are -2.6°C and 50.4°C

48 respectively (Figure S1). Remote sensing analysis from 2002-2003 report average daily summer
49 temperatures as high as 45.3 to 55.7 C, with surface soil temperatures as high as 66.5 to 71.1 (Azizi et al.,
50 2007). The Lut Desert has a total area of ~ 51,800 km², and consists of sand dunes, ergs, mega-yardangs
51 (kaluts), desert pavement, as well as large flat areas of salty soils and playas (Alavipanah et al., 2007;
52 Ehsani, 2011). A semi-permanent river (Rud-e Shur) flows from NW of the area and passes the edge of
53 Kaluts and ends in the central depression (Chaleh Markazi).

54 The Lut Desert is within the Lut Block, whose basement consists of pre-Jurassic metamorphic rocks
55 (pelitic schist) as well as Jurassic sediments intruded by younger (Jurassic to Tertiary) granitic plutons
56 and covered by Tertiary mafic to felsic volcanics (Arjmandzadeh and Santos, 2014; Tirrul et al., 1983;
57 Yazdi et al., 2014). The region is active tectonically with many active faults (Boshrabadi et al., 2018).

58 A large portion of the region is too harsh for any plants, and has been referred to as aphytic (Mobayen,
59 1976) and devoid of life. However, recent work has described some of the extremophile microbial life
60 existing in the soils and their abilities to withstand high temperatures, UV light, and even radiation
61 (Mazkour et al., 2017; Mohseni et al., 2014; Shirsalimian et al., 2017). Although previous studies have
62 described the unusual desert geomorphology (Yazdi et al., 2014), there has been little attempt to
63 understand other surficial and shallow subsurface processes occurring there. In addition, the recent
64 expeditions discovered a shallow subsurface water system in at least a portion of this extremely hot place
65 (Stone, 2016; Trescher, 2017). As a first attempt to better understand the biodiversity and describe the
66 physical environment of the Lut Desert, and as part of a large scientific program (Adaptation and
67 Function of Lut Desert Biodiversity (AFLDB) project), we present the first geochemical data on these
68 waters, speculate on their origin and evolution, and compare them to what is known about other hyper-
69 arid environments in Israel, China, Chile, Australia and the western United States.

70 **METHODS**

71 The sampling coordinates and depths are given in Table 1, and sampling locations shown in Figure 1.
72 Surface water or shallow groundwater samples (~ 1 m depth) were taken by hand in pre-cleaned 120 ml
73 widemouth LDPE bottles. In some cases, overlying sediment/soil was removed by shovel prior to
74 sampling the water. The water samples were filtered through 0.4 μm membrane filters using precleaned
75 polycarbonate filtration system into a series of smaller precleaned LDPE bottles and stored in the dark at
76 ~ 4 °C until analysis. Major cations and anions were determined via ion chromatography after
77 appropriate dilution with MilliQ™ water (Lyons et al., 2005; Welch et al., 2010). Li and Sr were
78 measured by ICP-OES and Ni, Rb, Ba and Pb measured by ICP-MS on aliquots diluted such that the total
79 dissolved salts (TDS) were less than 1 g L⁻¹ and acidified to 2% v/v HNO₃. Filtration blanks were also
80 processed and analyzed as samples. Phosphate, NO₃⁻ + NO₂⁻, NH₄⁺ and H₄SiO₄ were measured using a
81 Skalar San++ nutrient analyzer. The bicarbonate concentration was determined by the difference in
82 charge balance between the measured cations and anions (Lyons et al., 2012). The precision of all directly
83 measured constituents was better than 10% (most were better than 5%), based on replicate analysis of
84 samples and standards (Welch et al., 2010). Our previous work suggests that HCO₃⁻ determined by charge
85 balance difference are usually better than ± 14% (Lyons et al., 2012). Water isotope composition, δD and
86 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, were determined using a Picarro water isotope analyzer (Carey et al., 2016).

88 Fig.1- Location of water (blue circles) and soil (red squares) sampling sites across the Lut Desert,
89 east Iran.

90 Table 1. Sample Locations and Descriptions.

Water Samples		
Sample ID	Location	Description
St 10	Lat 29° 34.831' N Long 58° 58.428' E	Sample obtained by digging into the sand dune at the depth of 80 cm below the land surface (Ab-e Yalan).
St 19	Lat 29° 48.780' N Long 59° 11.675' E	Location known as “Logger Point”. No Sign of surface water but dug into a brownish soil and reached water @ 90 cm depth. Image in Figure S2 .
St 21	Lat 30° 04.394' N Long 58° 55.298' E	Water off surface, flows for ~ 200 m and recharges (Sarcheshmeh-e Shoor Gaz)
St 22	Lat 30° 04.144' N Long 58° 56.153' E	Further downstream from #21, a very flat playa surrounded by scarpments. Known as Shoor Gaz Hamoun where surface discharge was sampled.

St 28	Lat 30° 24.025' N Long 58° 59.519' E	Low lying playa, Chale Malek-Mohammad sampled water from swamp area. Image in Figure S2 .
Soil Samples		
Sample ID	Location	Description
2	Lat 30° 58.20' N Long 57° 31.68' E	Small depression, 70 km N of Shahdad with sparse <i>Hammada salicornica</i> shrubs
5	Lat 31° 0.05' N Long 57° 40.80' E	Near saline river, Rude Shoore Gadom Berian
8	Lat 30° 55.35' N Long 58° 22.33' E	Mixture of Kalut soil profile and brown soil with some salt crystals near the Kal-e Lut
9	Lat 30° 53.90' N Long 58° 23.88' E	Brown soil from Lut Playa
13	Lat 30° 34.82' N Long 58° 35.62' E	Sand from Kalute Abul hol
18	Lat 30° 6.63' N Long 58° 43.57' E	Dagh (playa) of the eastern corner of Kalutes, scattered <i>Tamarix pycnocarpa</i> and <i>Suaeda fruticosa</i>
20	Lat 30° 2.53' N Long 58° 49.68' E	Sample from Shoorgaze Hamoun's puffy salt flat
25	Lat 29° 48.80' N Long 59° 11.68' E	Location known as "2005 Logger Point". Sample contains high moisture.
28	Lat 29° 45.58' N Long 59° 3.11' E	Water runnel between Shoor Gaz and southern Lut, <i>Seidlitzia rosmarinus</i> , <i>Tamarix kermanensis</i>
33	Lat 29° 20.80' N Long 59° 3.35' E	Mile Baluchena, <i>Desmostachys bipinnata</i>
37	Lat 29° 17.22' N Long 59° 5.58' E	Surface sample from Shahrokh-Abad Plain, <i>Seidlitzia Rosmarinus</i>

91

92 Soil samples were taken from the top 10-cm of the soil profile and stored in plastic bags. Air-
93 dried samples were passed through 2 mm sieve and diluted with distilled water following the method
94 described by Bolukbasi et al., (2015). Soil conductivity and pH was measured using a pH/Conductivity
95 meter (ORION STAR A215) by diluting samples with distilled water to 1:2.5 and 1:5, respectively. The
96 percentage of gypsum content in the soil was determined gravimetrically by comparing samples dried at
97 60 °C and 105 °C (Porta et al., 1986). Total carbon (C_t) was measured by elemental analyzer following the
98 Dumas method (Elementar C/N; VarioMax, Hanau, Germany). All soil measurements were conducted at
99 Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología (IPE-CSIC), Spain.

100 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

101 The water geochemistry data and soil chemical parameters are shown in Table 2 and 3, respectively. A
102 number of general observations of these data can be made. All the waters are Na-Cl, but they are unlike

103 seawater derived brines in that $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$ and $\text{HCO}_3^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ (Figure 2). The K concentrations are
 104 uniformly low relative to Na. Unlike some hypersaline waters in extremely hyper arid environments, the
 105 Li, Mg, and Br concentrations are relatively low (Long et al., 1992; Lyons and Welch, 1997; Vengosh,
 106 2013). In fact, the increasing Cl:Br ratios with increasing Cl^- suggest extensive halite dissolution has
 107 helped increase the Cl concentration relative to Br in these waters (Figure 3) (McCaffrey et al., 1987).
 108 With the possible exception of sample 10, the N:P ratios are extremely high, $\sim 20,000$ to $30,000:1$, much
 109 higher than found in most natural waters (Bernier and Bernier, 2012; Schlesinger and Bernhardt, 2013).
 110 These high concentrations of $\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$ indicate the accumulation of NO_3^- within the landscape,
 111 minimal biological uptake of N, and the lack of extensive denitrification within the shallow groundwater
 112 (Figure 3).

114 **Figure 2. Piper diagram of water samples collected from the Lut Dessert, with seawater plotted for**
 115 **comparison. Lut Dessert shallow groundwaters are all Na-Cl brines. Seawater data from Pilson,**
 116 **(2012).**

117

118 The accumulation of soluble salts in a landscape occurs when evaporation exceeds precipitation
 119 and there is little to no flushing of the salts. Shallow saline groundwater can develop from a combination
 120 of two important processes: by meteoric waters being evaporated, hence concentrating the solutes along
 121 its flow path, and by the dissolution of previously accumulated salts. The former process can be traced by
 122 a change in water isotope signals (i.e. δD and $\delta^{18}O$) with salinity, while the latter through the observance
 123 of an increase in the ratios of certain solutes such as Cl:Br with salinity (Vengosh, 2013). As noted above
 124 and seen in Table 2, the Cl:Br of these waters increase with Cl⁻ (Figure 3), suggesting strongly that the
 125 dissolution of previously deposited halite is a major control on the overall salinity of these waters. This
 126 appears to be particularly the case in the three most saline samples where the Cl:Na ratio is ~ 1 (Table 2,
 127 Figure 3). This same phenomenon has been observed in other parts of Iran (Jalali, 2007; Nassery and
 128 Kayhomayoon, 2013).

129 **Table 2. Water chemistry for Lut Dessert samples.**

	Cl	SO ₄	NO ₃ N	Br	F	HCO ₃
	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM
St 10	284	40.6	0.866	0.099	0.035	75.5
St 19	783	21.9	12.34	0.019	na	41.2
St 21	634	32.7	8.72	0.019	na	36.9
St 22	1874	28.9	30.85	0.027	0.032	263
St 28	5373	5.3	82.83	0.052	0.119	66

	Na	K	Mg	Ca	Li	Sr
	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM	mM
St 10	394	2.01	10.8	12.3	0.718	0.187
St 19	688	1.86	13.9	81.3	0.189	0.702
St 21	596	1.54	22.3	51.7	0.225	0.506

St 22	1910	6.77	65.3	94.5	0.647	1.11
St 28	5250	8.86	89.3	353	2.18	3.27

	P PO₄	N NH₄	NO₂+NO₃	Si	δ¹⁸O	δD
	μM	μM	mM	μM	‰	‰
St 10	1.58	8.54	1.13	340	-3.35	-19.96
St 19	0.53	21.4	12.3	282	5.64	-14.16
St 21	0.33	24.5	9.00	262	4.46	-14.65
St 22	1.04	46.0	35.1	279	6.35	-9.11
St 28	2.56	97.5	81.5	169	17.86	26.91

ICP MS	Ni	Rb	Ba	Pb	TDS
	μg/l	μg/l	μg/l	μg/l	g/kg
St 10	24.5	43.6	125	1.5	27.9
St 19	112	46.4	139	1.0	50.8
St 21	84.7	26.8	71.2	2.0	43.4
St 22	150	79.6	141	5.4	127.2
St 28	520	134	826	23.0	281.2

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131

132 **Table 3. Chemical properties of soil samples from Lut Desert.**

Sample ID	pH	EC μS/cm	C_t %	Gypsum Wt %
2	9.12	859	0.95	8.92
5	8.57	836	1.16	17.59
8	7.92	4481	0.89	60.68
9	7.96	5780	1.12	71.00
13	9.18	1160	0.33	2.75
18	8.62	370	1.58	6.01
20	8.28	9210	1.05	50.79
25	8.89	1513	0.86	8.57
28	9.10	560	1.67	5.50
33	8.91	1298	1.92	7.43
37	7.59	2884	1.74	41.17

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136 **Figure 3. Major ion ratio plots for water samples from the Lut Desert. a) Cl:Br vs Cl, b) NO₃+NO₂**
137 **vs Cl, c) Cl:Na vs Cl and d) Si:Cl vs Cl**

138

139 We used the Pitzer database in PHREEQC (US Geological Survey, v 3.4.0, Parkhurst and Appelo,
140 2013) to calculate the saturation state of a number of common binary salts in these brines (Table 4). We
141 were unable to measure pH in the field, so we have done these calculations using both pH 7 and 8,
142 although only the CaCO₃ polymorphs and dolomite are greatly affected by the pH variations. The pH of
143 the soil slurry measurements were all slightly alkaline (Table 3) with pH ranging from 7.59 to 9.18, thus
144 only the modelling results for pH 8 are presented in Table 4. Calculations were also done at 25, 50 and
145 70°C to estimate mineral saturation index (SI) over the range of temperatures expected in the field

146 (Alavipanah et al., 2007; Rahimzadeh et al., 2009). The carbonate minerals were supersaturated in all the
147 samples with greater saturation indices for samples with higher salinities (Table 3, 4). The saturation
148 index for carbonate minerals increased with temperature due to their retrograde solubility, suggesting that
149 increased temperature, as well as increased evaporation, should induce carbonate mineral precipitation
150 from these saline brines. All waters were at, or very near, equilibrium with respect to gypsum and
151 anhydrite (SI ranging from -0.64 to 0.34) with values generally increasing with increasing salinity. The
152 calculated SI values decrease with temperature for gypsum, but increase for anhydrite, suggesting that the
153 extreme temperatures in this environment favors the formation of anhydrite over gypsum. Most waters
154 were also slightly supersaturated or very near equilibrium with respect to barite at 25°C, except for the
155 most saline water (sample 28), which was slightly undersaturated. Though saturation index decreases with
156 increasing temperatures, suggesting that barite precipitates could start dissolving in the brines at *in situ*
157 conditions. With the exception of sample 10, most of the brines were slightly supersaturated with respect
158 to celestite (SrSO₄), and like barite, SI decreases with increasing temperature, suggesting that the
159 temperature variations described in this environment could be important controls for the solubility of Ca,
160 Sr, Ba, and SO₄ in these shallow brines. The soil data from the top 10 cm support these calculations in
161 that the abundant total soil carbon content (C_{Total}) values range from ~ 1 to 2% suggesting significant
162 amounts of CaCO₃. The gypsum concentrations are also very high but quite variable, with values
163 between 2.75 and 71% of the total soil mass (Table 3). There is a correlation (R²=0.68) between gypsum
164 content of soil and EC suggesting evaporation has played a major role in chemical evolution of both soil
165 and brine in the Lut Desert (Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure S3). Most of the waters were slightly
166 undersaturated with respect to amorphous SiO₂. Halite is undersaturated except in the most saline brine
167 sample (Sample 28). These calculations, along with the soil data suggest that the precipitation of gypsum
168 (CaSO₄•2H₂O) or anhydrite (CaSO₄), and the dissolution of previously deposited NaCl, are major
169 controls on the Na⁺, Ca²⁺, SO₄²⁻ and Cl⁻ concentration in these waters and that the upper limit of the
170 H₄SiO₄ is probably controlled by amorphous SiO₂ precipitation. The latter hypothesis is also supported
171 by the decrease of Si:Cl with increasing Cl concentration (Figure 2), which indicates that Si is not

172 behaving conservatively as the brine is concentrating. The low K concentrations and the high Ca:Mg
 173 ratios may suggest that K^+ and Mg^{2+} concentrations are controlled by either adsorption of K and Mg onto
 174 silicate minerals, or authigenic clay mineral formation. Similar K loss has been observed along the flow
 175 path of shallow groundwaters in the Atacama Desert (Magaritz et al., 1989). Except for sample 10, the
 176 Ca/Sr ratios are very similar to seawater (mean Ca/Sr 103 compared to seawater Ca/Sr of 113). Sample
 177 10 more closely reflects the crustal ratio (of 66), indicating along with the highest H_4SiO_4 that this water
 178 reflects a chemical weathering component that becomes less significant at higher salinities. The
 179 concentrations of most trace elements detected (Li, Ni, Rb, Ba, Sr, Pb, as well as NH_4^+) generally
 180 correlate with salinity of the brines. The wetting and drying cycles are important in this system as
 181 demonstrated by both the very high Cl:Br ratios, and the mineral saturation calculations, which, as noted
 182 above, indicate that the dissolution of previously deposited NaCl is a very significant process. Drever and
 183 Smith, (1978) have demonstrated that cyclic wetting and drying in arid climates can lead to brines
 184 depleted in SO_4^{2-} , Mg^{2+} and Si relative to Cl^- , similar to what we observe in these waters. This is due to
 185 the kinetics of dissolution of previously deposited salts with the most soluble salts redissolving more
 186 readily than the less soluble salts.

187 **Table 4 Saturation Indices of common binary salts calculated at 25, 50 and 70°C and pH 8 for Lut**
 188 **Desert water samples.**

189

Mineral	St 10	St 19	St 20	St 21	St 28
pH 8 25°C					
Anhydrite	-0.64	-0.31	-0.28	-0.23	0.26
Gypsum	-0.3	0.01	0.05	0.05	0.2
Barite	0.66	0.25	0.18	0.1	-0.56
Celestite	-0.15	-0.03	0.06	0.02	0.5
Aragonite	2	2.58	2.31	3.58	4.29
Calcite	2.28	2.87	2.59	3.87	4.57
Dolomite	4.55	5.05	4.91	7.55	8.79
Halite	-2.86	-2.17	-2.33	-1.24	0.57
$SiO_2(a)$	-0.77	-0.8	-0.85	-0.65	-0.19
pH 8 50°C					
Anhydrite	-0.36	-0.04	-0.01	0.05	0.32
Gypsum	-0.31	0	0.04	0.04	0

Barite	0.41	-0.03	-0.08	-0.19	-0.87
Celestite	-0.06	0.05	0.15	0.13	0.48
Aragonite	2.27	2.84	2.57	3.79	4.39
Calcite	2.6	3.18	2.9	4.13	4.72
Dolomite	5.22	5.69	5.55	8.06	9.06
Halite	-2.9	-2.21	-2.37	-1.27	0.48
SiO ₂ (a)	-0.99	-1.03	-1.07	-0.89	-0.59
pH 8 70°C					
Anhydrite	-0.14	0.17	0.21	0.25	0.34
Gypsum	-0.28	0.01	0.05	0.04	-0.17
Barite	0.25	-0.21	-0.26	-0.4	-1.09
Celestite	0	0.1	0.2	0.17	0.43
Aragonite	2.46	3.02	2.75	3.95	4.48
Calcite	2.8	3.37	3.09	4.29	4.83
Dolomite	5.53	5.99	5.85	8.28	9.14
Halite	-2.92	-2.23	-2.39	-1.28	0.41
SiO ₂ (a)	-1.14	-1.18	-1.23	-1.07	-0.87

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191

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Figure 4 The correlation between soil's electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) and gypsum content (%) in soil samples from Lut Desert.

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195

The stable isotopes of water are shown in Table 2 and plotted in Figure 5A. The global meteoric water line as well as the local meteoric water lines (LMWL) for Tehran and snowmelt from the Zagros

196 Mountains to the north and west of the Lut Desert are plotted for comparison (Mosaffa et al., 2015; Osati
 197 et al., 2014). The least saline sample (10) plots closest to the meteoric lines and is also similar to the
 198 modeled “isoscapes” precipitation value for this general region (Bowen and Revenaugh, 2003). Samples
 199 21, 19 and 22 plot obliquely to the LMWLs (Figure 5A) suggesting extensive evaporation, while sample
 200 28, the most saline water, plots very far off the lines indicating massive evaporative loss. These data
 201 coupled with the Cl:Br values strongly indicate that both extensive evaporation and salt dissolution have
 202 played a role in producing these hypersaline waters.

203

204 **Figure 5A) Isotope data plots and 5B) the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ -TDS relationship for Lut Desert water samples.**

205

206 Spatial distribution patterns of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and δD values show significant depletion from station 28 to
 207 station 10 (Fig. 6, Fig. S4), where a one degree equatorward shift causes around 21 and 48‰ depletion in
 208 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and δD values, respectively. The observed gradients in isotopic values of Lut water samples are too
 209 high to be explained by the latitude effect (e.g. Bershaw et al., 2012; Bowen and Wilkinson, 2002). The
 210 effect of altitude as well as the amount of precipitation (altitude and amount effects) cannot explain such a
 211 shift either, due to very low annual precipitation and low elevation gradient in Lut desert. A strong
 212 correlation ($R^2=0.8$) is observed in changes in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values with respect to total dissolved solid (TDS),

213 Fig.5B. This observation supports the idea that a high gradient shift in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and δD values are related to
214 the salinity of waters caused by evaporation processes (Conroy et al., 2014).

215

216 **Figure 6 Gradient of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (left) and $\delta^2\text{H}$ (right) in the Lut Desert. Arrows denote gradient vectors.**

218 Implications for Other Hyper-Arid Environments

219 We have reviewed the available data from a number of other hyper-arid regions, and the
220 geochemistry of the soils/shallow groundwaters have great similarities. Shallow groundwaters in Death
221 Valley/Mojave Desert, USA, the Atacama, Chile, and the Turpan Basin, NW China have high TDS, and
222 are primarily Na-Cl waters, although some Na-SO₄ waters also exist (Boutt et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2014;
223 Thomas et al., 1996). These waters are evapoconcentrated meteoric waters that have also solubilized
224 previously deposited evaporite minerals, such as gypsum, mirabilite and halite (Chen et al., 2014;
225 Magaritz et al., 1989; Thomas et al., 1996). All of this information indicates that periodic wetting and the

226 precipitation/dissolution cycling of soluble salts play a very important role in controlling the
227 geochemistry of all these waters. The vadose zones of these environments, as well as the shallow
228 groundwaters, can accumulate large amounts of very soluble ions, such as nitrate (Finstad et al., 2016;
229 Lybrand et al., 2013; Qin et al., 2012). High $\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$ concentrations in groundwater are observed in
230 other hyper-saline systems such as the Negev Desert, and Central Australia (Barnes et al., 1992;
231 Rosenthal et al., 1987). This NO_3^- is presumably deposited from the atmosphere and accumulates over
232 time (Böhlke et al., 1997; Lyons et al., 2016) or was initially fixed biologically, oxidized and flushed
233 from the unsaturated zone (Barnes et al., 1992; Rosenthal et al., 1987). Associated with the nitrate can be
234 both perchlorate and iodate salts (Lybrand et al., 2016). We have observed another unidentified peak in
235 the anion chromatograms which falls where the perchlorate anion would generally be seen. Perchlorate
236 has been observed in other hyperarid regions in the world, including the Atacama and the McMurdo Dry
237 Valleys of Antarctica (Ericksen, 1981; Jackson et al., 2015, 2012). In all these environments a high
238 percentage of this nitrate originates from the atmosphere, suggesting, like in the Lut Desert, the role of
239 biological processes in controlling N distribution is probably minor. Our data from the Lut, when
240 compared to these other settings, suggest that the processes that control the geochemistry of these surficial
241 and shallow subsurface environments are similar. The abundance of NO_3^- , and the potential presence of
242 perchlorate, suggests little biological alteration of these very soluble salts.

243 The accumulation of these salts in soils and shallow groundwaters and the partitioning between the
244 two are related to the stability of the landscape, the climate, and the landscape age, as previously noted by
245 Lybrand et al., (2016). Additions of water clearly can remove salts from the soils solubilizing and
246 transporting them into the shallow groundwaters. Conversely, extensive hyper-aridity can lead to the
247 precipitation of salts. Cation exchange and possibly authigenic aluminosilicate mineral formation in the
248 shallow groundwaters can influence K concentrations, as we have observed in the Lut and others have
249 observed in desert waters (Magaritz et al., 1989), as well as influence both the vertical and horizontal
250 distribution of soluble binary salts in soils (Boutt et al., 2016; Finstad et al., 2016; Lybrand et al., 2013).

251 The lack of halite saturation may also suggest that the basin is not hydrologically closed and water is
252 being lost at depth through leakage as outlined in Wood and Sanford, (1990) and Rosen, (1994), as non-
253 evaporative groundwater loss can result in steady state solute concentrations that do not approach more
254 soluble salt deposition (Wood and Sanford, 1990). As noted above, the Lut Block is highly faulted, and
255 tectonic controls on groundwater geochemistry in Iran have previously been noted (Masoodi and
256 Rahimzadeh, 2018).

257 **CONCLUSIONS**

258 We present, to our knowledge, the first geochemical analysis of water from one of the hottest locations on
259 the Earth, the Lut Desert, Iran. The data indicate that the salinity of these waters is produced by both
260 evaporative processes and dissolution of previously deposited salts, and thus wetting and drying are very
261 important factors in controlling brine geochemical evolution. Thermodynamic calculations indicate that
262 waters are essentially in equilibrium with gypsum and are also highly supersaturated with respect to
263 carbonate minerals. Chemical weathering of aluminosilicate minerals, in what we assume to be the fresher
264 regions of the flow systems, produce high H_4SiO_4 concentrations that may be later controlled by
265 equilibrium with amorphous SiO_2 precipitation as water is lost and brine becomes more saline. Soluble
266 ions such as NO_3^- are found at very high concentrations in these waters suggesting little to no removal via
267 biological processes. However other soluble ions that sometimes accumulate in hypersaline environments
268 are not evapoconcentrated to a great extent. The data presented within adds important new information on
269 the geochemical evolution of hyper-arid environments from a system heretofore undescribed.

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433

Figure 3 Major ion ratio plots for water samples from the Lut Desert. a) Cl:Br, b) NO₂+NO₃, c) Cl:Na, and d) Si:Cl versus Cl.

Fig.4 The correlation between soil's electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) and soil's gypsum content (%) in soil samples from Lut Desert.

Figure 5a) Isotope data plots and 5b) the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ -TDS relationship for Lut Desert water samples.

Supplemental figures for Lyons et al., The hydrogeochemistry of shallow groundwater from the Lut Desert: The hottest place on Earth.

Figure S1. Annual mean precipitation and annual mean max. and min. temperature averaged over the 7 years (2003-2010) at Shahdad (at the edge of the Lut's west flank).

Figure S2. a) Site 28 showing shallow groundwater and salt crusts (footprints in the foreground for scale) and b) Site 19 (Logger Point) collecting shallow groundwater.

Figure S3. Spatial distribution for electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) (left) and soil gypsum content (%) (middle) and total carbon (right) in soil samples from Lut Desert. Dashed rectangle corresponds to the area where water samples were collected. Elevated soil EC and gypsum are coincident with elevated salt content of water samples and evaporative signal in water isotopes.

Figure S4. Plots of water isotopes as a function of Latitude.